

STEP 3 - Application survey topics 1 - 8

This section provides an overview and explanations for step 3: the main survey. In step 2 of the survey, we have determined how many applications we will score per paper. Be sure to note these down, so each application score set performed here can be matched with the paper scores from step 2.

This survey consists of 8 main topics, each consisting of several questions.

Good luck!!

* Required

1. Email address *

Paper ID

double check
double double check

2. what's the paper ID *

3. what's the first authors' family name (to triple check) *

4. What's the application letter + name? (if only one application, just put "A") *

5. **WARNING BOX - ONLY** fill in if there is a problem with this response! explain the problem in short, and post a message in the classroom with application letter + name.

topic 1:
Methods
and
their use

This section will take you through some questions to inventory which methods have been used in this application. This step is very important as it needs to allow us to look at patterns per method once we have the full database. There is an expanding list of valuation methods being compiled. You have this list in the manual. To be sure not to miss anything, we would like you to do two things here:

1. count the NUMBER of MAIN valuation methods and ADDITIONAL valuation methods:

A 'MAIN' METHOD: a valuation method which provides the 'final' valuation results in this application, which is separately described, and for which separate results are presented centrally in this paper. Main methods should be applied to obtain, compare or combine 'final' valuation results in the application.

An ADDITIONAL METHOD is applied to provide input to the process, design or data of other method(s). We are not looking for each method or activity which is mentioned in passing or which generated a single variable! A minimum name, description and results, and a certain 'valuation activity' is required to mark it.

!!! if several methods are contrasted and applied independently, and described in full, please reconsider if these aren't separate applications, see step 2 survey. If so, go back via your editing link and correct the scores there (and here).

2. compile a LIST of each, referring to our methods list or adding new and/or related methods:

!!! please be tidy:

- use numbers for literally listed methods,
- use name and reference for new ones,
- add "(linked to XX) if you think the new method is linked (even a synonym!) to one we have, and
- use semicolons ";" to separate the methods.

[Example: 15; 38; 46; some method (someone et al. 2016, linked to 56); 161.]

!!! check if the count adds up: if you marked 3 methods, you should have 3 numbers/names on the list.

6. 1.1 - Nr. of main valuation methods *

7. 1.2 - Carefully list ALL main valuation methods *

8. 1.3 - Nr. of additional/supporting valuation methods *

9. 1.4 - Carefully list ALL additional valuation methods (put "/" if 0) *

10. 1.5 - In this application, the goal of combining valuation methods is (multiple possible) *

Check all that apply.

- to compare methods
- to obtain integrated valuation results
- to provide specific input (proces/design/data) to a main method
- unclear
- no methods are combined

Other: _____

11. 1.6 - Explain in short how valuation method(s) above were combined

FROM NOW
ON...

Focus all following scores on THIS application and THIS main method(s).

You have defined the 'units of analysis' now: please stick to it.

In case of multiple applications and methods, make a note on a piece of paper. Don't get lost :-)

End of Topic 1
- Methods
and their use

That's it! you just filled in which methods were applied and how they were combined for this valuation. Just one confidence question and then ... moving on. 7 more sections to go.

12. 1.7 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this step? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

13. 1.8 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Topic 2 - Context of
application

This topic has questions on the physical, spatial, temporal and socio-political context of the application.

14. 2.1 - The application addresses the following (administrative) spatial scale(s) (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- local (incl. village, parish, municipality, town, city)
- district, county
- administrative region (as sub-national), (incl. province, state)
- cross-national or cross-region Indigenous territories/jurisdictions/lands
- cross-national or cross-region protected areas
- national, federal
- regional as multi-national
- continental
- global
- Option 9

Other: _____

15. 2.2 - The application assesses the following habitats (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Forests
- Savannah
- Deserts
- Grasslands
- Shrublands
- Wetlands – peatlands, mires, bogs
- Mountain habitats
- Urban / Semi-urban
- Cultivated areas
- Aquaculture
- Inland surface water and water bodies / freshwater
- Coastal areas
- Deep sea
- unclear
- Irrelevant

Other: _____

16. 2.3 - The application USES data COLLECTED at the biophysical scale of (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- field plot/individual organism
- local ecosystem/organism population
- regional ecosystem/organism population
- global ecosystem/organism population
- unclear
- irrelevant / no biophysical data used

17. 2.4 - The application draws valuation CONCLUSIONS at the biophysical scale of (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- field plot/individual organism
- local ecosystem/organism population
- regional ecosystem/organism population
- global ecosystem/organism population
- unclear
- irrelevant / no biophysical data used

18. 2.5 - The application uses data COLLECTED at the social scale of (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- individuals
- households
- specific stakeholder groups/ communities
- society (full human population of the area)
- unclear
- irrelevant / no values are collected from people

19. 2.6 - The application draws valuation CONCLUSIONS at the social scale of (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- individuals
- households
- specific stakeholder groups/ communities
- society (full human population of the area)
- unclear
- irrelevant / no values are collected from people

20. 2.7 - The application collected data with the following temporal frequency: *

Mark only one oval.

- once
- continuous / repeated
- unclear

21. 2.8 - The application assesses values change over time: *

Mark only one oval.

- yes (e.g. assessing a change in state, or trend)
- no (only a state is assessed)

22. 2.9 - The application assesses following temporal changes: (tick 'irrelevant' if you answered 'no' on previous question) *

Check all that apply.

- past-present / very short (less than 1 year)
- past-present / short (1-3 years)
- past-present / medium (4-10 years)
- past-present / long term (10+ years)
- present-future / very short (less than 1 year)
- present-future / short (1-3 years)
- present-future / medium (4-10 years)
- present-future / long term (10+ years)
- unclear
- irrelevant

23. 2.10 - There are multiple classifications of 'what is valued'. We want to know how these fit in the IPBES categories. The application assesses the following 'targets of valuation' regarding Nature Itself (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Individual organisms (e.g. the sacred village tree)
- Biophysical assemblages
- Biophysical processes
- Biodiversity
- Maintenance of options
- none

Other: _____

24. 2.11 - There are multiple classifications of 'what is valued'. We want to know how these fit in the IPBES categories. The application assesses the following 'targets of valuation' regarding Regulating Nature Contributions To People (ecosystem services) (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Maintenance of options
- Habitat creation and maintenance
- Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules
- Regulation of air quality
- Regulation of climate
- Regulation of ocean acidification
- Regulation of freshwater quantity, flow and timing (!includes water provision!)
- Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality
- Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments
- Regulation of hazards and extreme events
- None

Other: _____

25. 2.12 - There are multiple classifications of 'what is valued'. We want to know how these fit in the IPBES categories. The application assesses the following 'targets of valuation' regarding Material Nature Contributions To People (ecosystem services) (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Energy
- Food and feed
- Materials
- Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources
- None

Other: _____

26. 2.13 - There are multiple classifications of 'what is valued'. We want to know how these fit in the IPBES categories. The application assesses the following 'targets of valuation' regarding non-material NCP (or ES) (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Learning and inspiration
- Physical and psychological experiences
- Supporting identities
- None

Other: _____

27. 2.14 - There are multiple classifications of 'what is valued'. We want to know how these fit in the IPBES categories. The application assesses the following 'targets of valuation' regarding People's quality of life (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Living well in harmony with nature
- Identity and Autonomy
- Spirituality and Religions
- Art and Cultural heritage
- Sustainability and Resilience
- Diversity and Options
- Governance and Justice
- Health and Wellbeing
- Education and Knowledge
- Good social relations
- Security and Livelihoods
- None

Other: _____

28. 2.15 - The application assesses multiple values and brings them together into an 'overall value' or importance by: *

Check all that apply.

- Bringing them together by converting all values to a common unit
- Bringing them together and assigning weights to individual value targets based on researcher defined (or even) weights
- Bringing them together and assign weights to individual value targets based on a group discussion about acceptable weights given to different values
- Keeping the results from the study of the separate value and use the results as a basis for a group discussion.
- The application assesses multiple values as bundles and do not attempt to weigh individual value targets
- The application asks respondents or participants to rank options including multiple values and infer the weight of individual components from their ranking.
- unclear: method of bringing values together is not explained
- irrelevant: application does not attempt to bring the different values together
- Other: _____

29. 2.16 - The application mentions interests and conflicts: *

Mark only one oval.

- no different interests or conflicts mentioned
- non-conflictual differences in interests: mentioning of various interests to be considered but NO mentioning of actual verbal or physical harm.
- conflict : mentioning of verbal, political or even physical conflict between interest groups over the assessed values
- unclear

30. 2.17 - Are the valuation results taken up or not? How is the uptake/use documented? *

Mark only one oval.

- Desired uptake - A potential, expected, or wished for use of outputs, sometimes only cursory)
- Testing use case - Researcher initiated valuation study, reported test of use to enable decision making
- Actual use case - Stakeholder commissioned valuation study, reported use to enable decision making

31. 2.18 - Are valuation results taken up for (or aimed at) informative, decisive, or technical purposes (multiple possible)? *

Check all that apply.

- Informative - Formative or Affirmative (Value formation or affirmation (not used decisively or for technical purposes))
- Informative - Awareness raising (Advocacy and raising awareness of total value, trade-offs, conflicts, scenarios)
- Informative - Justification (ex post of a decision, Evaluation of existing projects and policies ex post)
- Informative - Accounting & Indicators (Assessment of historic trends)
- Decisive - Recommendations & guidance (Guidances, strategies, plans)
- Decisive - Participation (Negotiation, arguments for discussion, shared norms & conflict resolution // Formulation of decision problem and structuring)
- Decisive - Prioritization on Trade-offs (screening alternatives // ranking alternatives)
- Decisive - Environmental management criterion (Policy target-setting // Criteria for spatial targeting (zoning, planning) // Allocation of rights to land and natural resource use)
- Technical - Price-setting (Environmental standard setting (implicit pricing) // Pricing, setting incentive levels (explicit pricing))
- Technical - Damage compensation (Establishing levels of damage compensation)
- unclear

Other: _____

Skip to question 32

End of Topic 2 - Context of Application

Well done! Just one confidence question and then ... moving on. 6 more topics to go.

32. 2.20 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this step? *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure

33. 2.21 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Topic 3 - Application descriptors

34. 3.1 - Elicitation process: through what process were values collected? *

Check all that apply.

- Individuals written responses to questions
 - Individual responses face-to-face, phone or similar responses
 - Individual responses following a group discussion
 - Group responses to the valuation question
 - Obtaining information from transactions in markets
 - Obtaining information from documents (policy/legal/historical texts)
 - Observing individual practices/behaviors
 - Observing group practices/behaviors
 - Obtaining information by observing biological aspects in real-time (e.g. recording bee visitation of flowers, counting birds, measuring biomass of trees)
 - Obtaining information by collecting measurement data over a period of time (e.g. weather data, sediments, nutrients etc.)
 - Obtaining information about biophysical indicators using secondary data (expert estimates, land use maps, satellite images, species Atlas data etc)
 - unclear
- Other: _____

35. 3.2 - The application uses or is based on data from the same spatiotemporal and socio-economic context (multiple answers possible in case of mixed/integrated methods): *

Check all that apply.

- data from the same context
 data transferred from other context(s)
 unclear

36. 3.3 - How are values articulated in this application? (e.g. time spent; number of people visiting; stated or narrated importance; avoided damage costs; healthy life years; species number; rarity; ...). Please state how the main results (from main methods) are represented in the paper. If multiple, make a list using semicolons ";" *

37. 3.4 - This application presents values in following form (multiple answers possible in case of mixed/integrated methods): *

Check all that apply.

- artistic (e.g. music, paintings, drawings, poetry)
 narrative (descriptions)
 categorical/nominal (e.g. types)
 ordinal expression (ranked types e.g. worse - better / low -high / small - big)
 cardinal expression (in numbers)

Other: _____

38. 3.5 - Aggregation: the application aggregates different stakeholders' values into an 'overall value or importance' by: *

Check all that apply.

- simple, non-weighted aggregation (averages or summations)
- weighted aggregation by a group process
- weighted aggregation by numerical weighting
- unclear: method of aggregation is not explained
- irrelevant: the method is not used to aggregate stakeholder's values

Other: _____

End of Topic 3 - Application descriptors

Well done! Just one confidence question and then ... moving on. 5 more topics to go.

39. 3.6 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this step? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

40. 3.7 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Topic 4 - Reliability and Validity

41. 4.1 - Replicability of the results is assessed *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 unclear

42. 4.2 - Consistency of the results is assessed *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 unclear

43. 4.3 - Precision of the results is assessed *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 unclear

44. 4.4 - Internal Validity of the results is assessed by *

Check all that apply.

- credibility
 construct validity
 content validity
 criterion validity
 community validity
 unclear
 not assessed

Other: _____

45. 4.5 - External Validity of the results is assessed by *

Check all that apply.

- transferability
 generalisability
 unclear
 not assessed

Other: _____

End of Topic 4 - Reliability and Validity

That's it! Just one confidence question and then ... moving on.
4 more topics to go.

46. 4.6 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this step? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

47. 4.7 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Topic 5 - Indigenous Peoples & Like-minded Local communities

48. 5.1 - Are there any authors from Indigenous Peoples or Like-minded Local Communities? *

Mark only one oval.

- none
- one or more authors explicitly represented as such
- unclear

49. 5.2 - The application identifies/assesses respect towards nature by (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

generally demonstrating and expressing deep respect to the land, sea, or their natural surroundings; manifestation of spiritual connection to the land showing intimate interaction associated with the land, sea, lakes or rivers; spiritual beings in the landscape; sacred sites.

identifying placed-based community ceremonies, rituals or gatherings that are linked to the terrestrial or marine landscape.

respecting those ceremonies, rituals or gatherings

does not assess this

Other: _____

50. 5.3 - The application assesses responsibility or care for the land by (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

assessing overall protection & preservation of sites (mountains, rivers, landscapes, landforms, forests, etc.) for their sacred meaning, or cultural or historical significance;

assessing whether actions/practices where natural resources use is compatible with and follows ancestral teachings about living in harmony with nature and respect for the land;

Identifying non-over-exploitative production systems out of a sense of responsibilities towards future generations

considering actions/practices to renew the sense of interconnection with terrestrial or marine surroundings and awareness about responsibility and care.

does not assess this

Other: _____

51. 5.4 - The application assesses kinship/communality with other people by (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- assessing equitable sharing use of seasonal resources,
 considering the satisfaction of community members' needs, particularly women, elders and children.
 assessing whether the community shares teachings and knowledge on how to live sustainably with all elements of nature
 assessing the community internal practices of reciprocity (communal work or sharing of products); equitable trade with other communities.
 does not assess this

Other: _____

52. 5.5 - The application assesses kinship/communality with non-human entities by (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- identifying and assessing kinship relationships with animal through time identifying and assessing kinship relationships with animals' habitat and other plant species
 identifying some plants as sacred,
 assessing the reluctance and discouragement of using plants, animals, mountains, rivers, and other non-living entities in nature for individualistic gains
 assessing the understanding of landforms as entitled to personhood or legal rights
 does not assess this

Other: _____

53. 5.6 - The application assesses values of self-determination and ancestral law, by (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- assessing the application of ancestral law, teachings, customs and uses,
- assessing the acknowledgement and inclusion of people's beliefs, spirituality, and ceremonial practices
- assessing the community governance and community protocols or regulations,
- assessing the implementation of the FPIC,
- accounting for the intervention of Indigenous spiritual authorities and use of Indigenous language,
- including the Indigenous authors' self-positioning or elders and knowledge-keepers authorship
- does not assess this

Other: _____

End of Topic 5 -
IPLMLC

That's it! Just one confidence question and then ... moving on. 4 more topics to go.

54. 5.7 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this step? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

55. 5.8 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Topic 6 - Human Well-being

56. 6.1 - The application assesses human well-being using one of the following indicators (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Livelihood dependence on access to natural resources
- Livelihood dependence on management of land
- Profits from natural resources
- Physical health outcomes linked to nature & biodiversity
- Mental health outcomes linked to nature & biodiversity
- Subjective well-being (e.g., satisfaction, happiness etc.) linked to nature & biodiversity
- Change in utility of individuals linked to changes in nature & biodiversity
- A composite indicator (combining different aspects of well-being into one, such as Human Development Index, Better Life Index etc.) linked to nature and biodiversity
- Well-being indicator is assessed but not linked to nature & biodiversity
- Application does not assess human wellbeing with one of these indicators

Other: _____

57. 6.2 - The application assesses the preferences (or importance) that humans assign to nature and biodiversity in terms of (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Hypothetical willingness to give up resources (monetary or other forms) to maintain (or increase) aspects of nature and biodiversity
- Hypothetical compensation (monetary or other forms) to give up access to nature or management rights of natural areas
- Scores of relative importance to people of nature's contributions to people (e. g. allocation of points to /or ranking of different aspects of nature or different places)
- Spending or expenditure (in monetary or other forms of resources) to maintain (or increase) aspects of nature and biodiversity (or to avoid losses)
- Dialogues with communities about the importance of different aspects of nature and biodiversity
- Application does not assess preferences of humans to nature

Other: _____

58. 6.3 - The application assesses the costs to protect nature & biodiversity for its own sake or to maintain nature's contributions to people in the form of (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

What has actually been spent in the past to protect nature and biodiversity or maintain nature's contribution to people [This only applies if the investment was done in the past]

The costs and the benefits from past projects to protect nature and biodiversity or maintain nature's contribution to people [This only applies if the project was in the past]

What it would cost (cost per unit) to protect nature and biodiversity or maintain nature's contribution to people

What it would cost to protect nature and biodiversity or maintain nature's contribution to people in the most effective way (i.e., compare different ways of meeting a target for nature and biodiversity or ES/NCPs)

The costs and the benefits from potential or hypothetical future projects or policies to protect nature and biodiversity or maintain nature's contribution to people

Application does not assess cost to protect nature & biodiversity for its own sake or to maintain nature's contributions to people

Other: _____

59. 6.4 - The application assesses human well-being in a different way, please specify

60. 6.5 - If the application assesses human well-being (specified above), is the well-being indicator assessed for different socio-demographic groups? *

Check all that apply.

- Yes, analysed for different income groups
- Yes, analysed for different age groups
- Yes, analysed for different levels of education
- Yes, analysed for different gender
- Yes, analysed for different stakeholder groups
- No, difference in the well-being indicator is assessed but not attributed to different socio-demographic groups
- No, difference in the well-being indicator by socio-demographic group is not evaluated.
- irrelevant
- Other: _____

End of topic 6: Human Well-being

That's it! Just one confidence question and then ... moving on. 2 more topics to go.

61. 6.6 How sure do you feel about your scores for this Topic? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

62. 6.7 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Topic 7 - Ecological Sustainability

63. 7.1 - The application assesses ecosystem condition by looking at (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Ecosystem health, healthy functioning of ecological processes
- Resilience of ecosystems, response to perturbation, recuperation
- Naturalness of ecosystem
- Biodiversity (not related to human use)
- Threatened species, extinction risk
- Degradation, impacts of drivers on the ecosystem
- application does not assess ecological condition

Other: _____

64. 7.2 - The application assesses ecosystem capacity by looking at the ecosystem side of (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Ecosystem services (potential) supply, stocks
- Ecosystem service flow, delivery, use
- Nature's contributions to people
- Viable populations of 'useful' species (Habitat suitability)
- Biodiversity (related to a human use, functional biodiversity)
- Quantity or quality of natural resources (related to a human use)
- application does not assess ecosystem capacity

Other: _____

65. 7.3 - The application assesses sustainable use / management of ecosystems by (multiple possible): *

Check all that apply.

- Ecological thresholds, boundaries, tipping points
- Maximum sustainable yield or harvest
- Carrying capacity for human use/pressure
- Restoration, Conservation effectiveness
- application does not assess sustainable use or management

Other: _____

End of topic 7: Ecological Sustainability

That's it! Just one confidence question and then ... moving on.
Only 1 more topic to go!!!

66. 7.4 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this Topic? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

67. 7.5 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Topic 8.1 - Distributive justice

The justice topic consists of 5 sections.

The first section of this Topic is about Distributive justice: intra- and intergenerational justice.

68. 8.1 - The application assesses intra-generational justice by: *

Check all that apply.

presenting benefits or costs disaggregated by different groups of people (e.g, by stakeholder type, livelihood, socio-demographic characteristics, location, country, etc),

estimating inequality using an index/indicator of inequality (e.g., Gini, HHI,)

assessing participants' perceptions of intragenerational justice, or of the (in)equality of distribution of gains and losses - with respect to how people think the distribution of outcomes ought to be;

assessing weights / importance of prioritising needs of disadvantaged groups (e.g. in welfare function, a weight on an indicator in an MCA, in discussions)

the application does not assess intra-generational justice

Other: _____

69. 8.2 - The application assesses inter-generational justice by looking at: *

Check all that apply.

- how values compare over time (using discounting, overtaking, Chichilnisky criteria, etc)
- values, benefits or costs disaggregated by generations
- future or past generations' needs, wants, values, or ability to live a good life by explicitly discussing these
- the application does not assess intergenerational justice

Other: _____

Topic 8.2 - Procedural justice

This second section on Justice is about Procedural Justice and how the application has designed and executed the process of valuation to address issues of representation, inclusiveness, participation, power and transparency.

70. 8.3 - Regarding the transparency of the valuation process, the application provides: *

Check all that apply.

- no info on the process
- a general description on the process, lacking detail on some steps of the process.
- detailed descriptions of the process
- Method's instruments (e.g. protocols and data collection material such as questionnaires) are shared with general public and study participants in a way suitable for those groups and in line with ethics regulations;
- Method's proceedings documentation (e.g. notes about meetings, discussions, decisions and appeals) are shared with general public, stakeholders and study participants in a way suitable for those groups and in line with ethics regulation
- Unclear

Other: _____

71. 8.4 - Representation of different stakeholders in the valuation process (in sampling, for participation) by: *

Check all that apply.

- discussing and reflecting on who was (not) represented (in the sample or among the participants)
- presenting results and data on representation (involvement in process) of different groups of people
- presenting results and data on statistical representativeness of the sample
- the application does not reflect on representation

Other: _____

72. 8.5 - The application identifies and targets stakeholder groups (for sample or for participation) primarily based on: *

Check all that apply.

- different interests in the use/management/protection of nature (e.g. farmers, bird watchers, extraction companies, local communities)
- different power or influence in the decision making (e.g. land owners, big companies, local inhabitants, landless people, tourists)
- political role or mandate (NGO, government rep, citizen group, private sector,..)
- gender
- age
- income and wealth
- rights of access and use of resources
- type of knowledge held (academic, technical, experience, indigenous,..)
- indigenous rights or worldviews
- other factors (e.g. disabled people)
- the application does not identify different groups

Other: _____

73. 8.6 - The application addresses inclusiveness of multiple stakeholders and minorities in the design of the valuation process by adjusting/providing: *

Check all that apply.

- Type of communication (verbal/written/visuals/otherwise)
- (Extra) time, place, costs (compensation)
- Child care
- Language(s) used
- Group composition and size
- The application does not mention any process design features to ensure inclusive participation of different stakeholders

Other: _____

74. 8.7 - Regarding internal power dynamics, the application: *

Check all that apply.

- Does not assess power dynamics of the application of the method in their case study in results or discussion
- Presents results and data on power dynamics (by e.g. showing speaking time, interruptions, use of physical space, testing difference in outputs in different power context...,)

75. 8.8 - Regarding participation level, the application: *

Check all that apply.

- Consulted participants as data providers, no clearly mentioned consent procedures (FPIC, GDPR-compliance).
- Consulted participants as data providers, with clear consent procedures (PFIC, GDPR-compliant),...).
- Consulted and discussed results and findings with participants
- Engaged stakeholders in every step, including question framing, method selection,, results and conclusions, reporting.
- Unclear
- The application does not take a participatory approach and/or does not involve human participants/respondents

Other: _____

Topic 8.3 - Recognition

Recognition is about the respect for different knowledge types, values, value types and reasons to value.

76. 8.9 - The application explicitly distinguishes and mentions the following types of knowledge: *

Check all that apply.

- Lay and experiential knowledge, held by consumers, citizens, general public
- Indigineous Local Knowledge, held by Indiginous Peoples or Like-minded Community members or representatives
- Scientific knowledge or academic expertise, held by academics or researchers
- Technical knowledge, held by people in relevant professions (excl. academics)
- Policy knowledge, held by policy makers, (excl. academics)
- The application does not explicitly mention (types of) knowledge

Other: _____

77. 8.10 - Recognition of broad values (1): the application assesses the following concepts (tick each group which contains a concept that is literally and explicitly assessed): *

Check all that apply.

- A: Livelihood security, human welfare and prosperity, happiness, responsibility (as sustainable use), intragenerational and intergenerational justice
- B: Responsibility as respectful cohabitation, coexistence, care (supporting regeneration, reducing harm), protecting the environment, stewardship, rights of nature, inter- and multispecies justice
- C: Tradition, enjoyment, beauty and aesthetic experience, inspiration, health, care (as maintenance, supporting regeneration, healing), awe, belonging and rootedness, bio-cultural diversity
- D: care, reciprocity, harmony with nature, reciprocal responsibilities, livelihood sovereignty, spiritual sovereignty, recognition justice, respect, responsibility and care for the land, kinship and interpenetration with non-human persons, self-determination
- none of the above

78. 8.11 - Recognition of broad values (2): does the application assess other value terms/concepts related/synonymous to the values listed above under A-D? In your answer, please provide the term/concept used in the paper, and the group to which this values pertains most in your opinion.

79. 8.12 - The application assesses the following types of values: *

Check all that apply.

- use values: direct use: consumptive (e.g. crops, livestock, aquaculture –provisioning ES)
- use values: direct use: non-consumptive (e.g. recreation, spiritual/cultural well-being, education –cultural ES)
- use values: indirect use (e.g. pest control, pollination, soil fertility – often regulating ES)
- option values (future use of known and unknown benefits)
- non-use values: philanthropic: bequest value (e.g. satisfaction of knowing future generation's benefits)
- non-use values: philanthropic: altruistic value (e.g. satisfaction of knowing other people's benefits)
- non-use values: biodiversity: existence value (e.g. satisfaction of knowing that species/ecosystem exists)
- unclear
- irrelevant

80. 8.13 - Value justification: the application has an emphasis on: *

Check all that apply.

- Instrumental (to achieve a particular end)
- Intrinsic (inherent worth, dignity of nonhuman beings, as well as non-instrumental values)
- Relational (that contribute to desirable relationships)
- Unclear
- irrelevant

Topic 8.4 - Community of justice

81. 8.14 - What/who are the subjects of justice? What humans or other entities are considered entitled to moral consideration? *

Check all that apply.

- A specific part of the current people
- All current people
- Future people
- Past people, ancestors, spirits
- Non-human beings
- Mother earth
- irrelevant

Other: _____

End of topic 8: Justice

That's it! Just one confidence question and then ... DONE!!

82. 8.15 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this step? *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure

83. 8.16 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

84. 8.17 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this ENTIRE APPLICATION (!all topics 1 to 8!) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

85. 8.18 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Crucial unclarity -
survey halted

You will be taken out of this application survey and we will check it. Don't worry. Take the next application!

86. Are you sure? No? - use the 'back' button below to go back to your previous question

Mark only one oval.

Yes

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